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Living Stakeholder Database

Methodology

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Executive Summary

Central to the INTERLACE project are the co-production of tools, governance instruments, and other project products as well as the exchange of knowledge to inform and support the restoration and rehabilitation of (peri-)urban ecosystems through Nature-based Solutions. In each partner city, the project products are co-produced, tested and validated through the local City Network Accelerator (CNA) which is composed of local stakeholders. Furthermore, INTERLACE products are tested and validated for wider applicability (beyond the participating cities) through the Impact Task Force (ITF) which is composed of project partners, local, regional and global stakeholders. Stakeholder analyses are conducted at each partner city to involve an inclusive range of local and relevant stakeholders in the local CNA and ITF. The stakeholder lists – including motivations on why they are considered a stakeholder – are stored in a living stakeholder database, which has the purpose to be updated over time as the project progresses and new insights arise.

This report presents the methodology of the stakeholder analysis used to create the INTERLACE living stakeholder databases. This report acts as a reference point for the INTERLACE knowledge brokers to apply the methodology in order to create or update their stakeholder database.

1. Introduction

Central to the INTERLACE project are the co-production of tools, governance instruments, and other project products as well as the exchange of knowledge to inform and support the restoration and rehabilitation of (peri-)urban ecosystems through Nature-based Solutions (NbS). In each partner city, the project products are co-produced, tested and validated through the local City Network Accelerator (CNA) which is composed of local stakeholders. City engagement and co-production activities are overseen by the respective City Focal Points (CFP) under the guidance of the respective task leads. Each CFP consists of the respective city representatives and a local research partner (referred to hereafter as *knowledge broker*). Furthermore, INTERLACE products will be tested and validated for wider applicability (beyond the participating cities) through the Impact Task Force (ITF) which is composed of project partners, local, regional and global stakeholders.

INTERLACE has introduced an agile framework for product development: a multi-stakeholder co-production approach (Del. 1.1 Guidance document about the INTERLACE agile workflow implementation). This aims to ensure the relevance, legitimacy and impact of all INTERLACE products for the targeted end users. To this end, small product development teams are created for each product as part of the co-production processes in the respective tasks.

A core part of INTERLACE is a genuine stakeholder engagement, which will optimize the collection and incorporation of available knowledge and experiences for the co-production of instruments and tools for restorative NbS. Stakeholder engagement can be defined as a broad, inclusive and continuous process and an open, constructive relationship between a project and those potentially affected by or interested in it for a purpose to achieve accepted outcomes (Durham et al. 2014; AccountAbility, 2015). Stakeholder engagement utilizes an inclusive, participatory approach to enable INTERLACE and wider actors to collaboratively address urban challenges and develop solutions.

INTERLACE aims to engage the stakeholders as early as possible in the project activities to optimize the collaboration on INTERLACE products and knowledge exchange. This provides the stakeholders the opportunity to provide their expertise and knowledge in the different phases of the INTERLACE project. It also contributes to creating a sense of ownership of the project activities and products.

The CFP of each INTERLACE city identified local challenges to which restorative NbS should respond to (Del. 1.3 Summary report on Joint City Forum). These include (but are not limited to) environmental and social challenges. To ensure just and multi-beneficial restorative NbS it is crucial to engage with an inclusive and diverse range of stakeholders to include different viewpoints, expertise and preferences. With these city challenges in mind, INTERLACE adapted the definition for local stakeholders from the Stakeholder Engagement Handbook (Durham et al. 2014) as follows:

“A stakeholder is any person or group who influences or is influenced by the city challenges”.

The **stakeholder analysis** is a crucial first step to ensure the engagement of an inclusive and diverse range of stakeholders. The aim of such analysis is to identify the local stakeholders of each INTERLACE city in relation to the city challenges. The method provides a structured approach to identify different types of stakeholders. Furthermore, it aims to provide a preliminary understanding of the interest of the identified stakeholders and the possible impact they could experience in relation to the city challenges and the restoration activities, as well as what the expected benefits are when

engaging the stakeholders in the local INTERLACE activities.

The results of the stakeholder analysis are used to select and invite stakeholders to participate in the local CNA's and other local INTERLACE activities. Furthermore, identified stakeholders will be invited to the ITF for the co-production of INTERLACE products.

The output of the stakeholder analysis will be collected into a **living stakeholder database** for each city. This allows for new stakeholders to be identified as the project progresses. The living stakeholder database can be updated as new insights are gained or developments occur. For example, stakeholders can be added, removed or the preliminary understanding of stakeholders can be updated after interacting with them. Thus, it is an **iterative process** in which the CFPs or other participants can provide new input after the creation of the initial stakeholder list.

This report presents the methodology of the stakeholder analysis used to create the INTERLACE living stakeholder databases. This report acts as a reference point for the knowledge brokers (responsible for conducting the stakeholder analysis) to apply the methodology in order to create or update their stakeholder database. The methodology was initially shared with the knowledge brokers in December 2020. The knowledge brokers applied the first iteration between February and March of 2021.

This first application resulted in the first versions of each cities' stakeholder database. These databases are incorporated into the INTERLACE logbook (only accessible for project partners). The INTERLACE logbook facilitates the collection and exchange of information that is relevant on project level. It contains key information on each city and helps to keep track of reporting needs.

The INTERLACE logbook ensures that the stakeholder databases are centrally stored and easily accessible for internal partners. It was not possible to include the databases in this report due to the size of the tables. Some snapshots as examples can be found in Annex 3.

2. Methodology

Due to Covid-19 restrictions, data collection happened through online meetings in each city. Therefore, this methodology focuses on preparing and conducting **online workshops**.

The methodology was developed from October to November 2020. INTERLACE partners (knowledge brokers, Work Package-leads, YES, NINA, Ecologic) had the opportunity to review the methodology and provide feedback. In December 2020, the methodology was discussed and shared with the knowledge brokers. The first iteration was applied by them before March 2021 to allow the results to be used for the selection and invitation of stakeholders for the CNA kick-off event held in March 2021.

To keep the stakeholder database up to date for following events, we encourage knowledge brokers to regularly reassess and update the living database (the authors will also send reminders).

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This chapter presents the steps to conduct the stakeholder analysis (figure 1). Section 2.1 presents practical guidance to prepare the data collection. Section 2.2 explains the different steps of the data collection. Section 2.3 provides guidance on assembling and analysing the data. Section 2.4 focuses on the iterative process of the stakeholder analysis.

Figure 1. Workflow of the INTERLACE Stakeholder Analysis.

2.1 Pre-workshop: Preparation

Several practical aspects can be prepared before the workshop to ensure a fruitful and efficient event:

- Invite participants to the stakeholder analysis that have a so-called ‘helicopter view’, meaning that they have knowledge about the city challenge(s) and, in relation to that, knowledge of stakeholders beyond their own domain/sector. Participants (with a ‘helicopter view’) can be people from within as well as outside the municipality. Snowball sampling¹ can be applied to identify new participants for following iterations (see section 2.4).
 - The starting point for the first iteration was the CFP. The city representatives within the CFP were expected to have a good overview of the challenges in the city, who is involved and who can participate in following iterations to update the stakeholder database.
- All participants need to sign the information and consent form before they can participate. A Google form was made available to share with the participants before the workshop. In case of a physical event, a Word version was made available which was printed and signed on the spot.
- Plan the workshop ahead of time, preferably with a Doodle when multiple participants attend.
- The data is collected in a Google sheet. A Google sheet has been prepared by the EV-INBO team and one was shared with each city. When a new and clean version is required, a copy can

¹ Snowball sampling is a method where initial participants are asked for recommendations for possible new participants based on their network and experience.

be made from the original sheet. After the workshop, the data collected in the Google sheet is transferred to the INTERLACE logbook.

- Data can be collected in the local language, to ensure that as many participants as possible can contribute during the workshop.
 - When necessary, data is translated to English afterwards. For example, the data of the first iteration was translated to English by the EV-INBO team in a separate document in order to use it for other project deliverables (for example Del. 1.5 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy and Del. 1.6 Protocol on cultural, gender and ethics-related considerations).
- Before conducting the stakeholder analysis, it is important to define the reasons why stakeholders are being identified, and in relation to what. In each city, this should be in relation to the identified city challenges (Del. 1.3) and preferably (not necessarily) in relation to a delineated location or intervention site. The more focused, clearly defined and easily understood the city challenges and location(s) are, the more targeted stakeholders can be identified and engaged.
- It is recommended to have a prioritization of city challenges, so that the challenges which are more likely to be addressed during the INTERLACE project are handled first during the workshop.
 - A first validation and prioritization of city challenges was done at the CNA kick-off event. This means that the stakeholder analysis and the local CNA events are both dependable of each other, as the stakeholders can provide input on the city challenges and the city challenges determine which stakeholders are relevant. The living stakeholder database should be updated accordingly through follow-up iterations, reflecting the course of the cities' ambitions within INTERLACE.
- When you estimate one workshop will not be sufficient e.g. due to the amount of city challenges to be handled during the stakeholder analysis, a two-tier approach can be applied (see section 2.1.1).
- It is recommended that each participant prepares an initial list of stakeholders. This list will be the starting point of the workshop. Therefore, the city challenges need to be communicated to the participants beforehand, so they can target the initial stakeholder identification.
 - For the first iteration, these questions were asked to the CFP members in break out groups during the City Forum in order to obtain an initial list of stakeholders. These questions can also be used for following iterations:
 - *Who are the key actors (internal and external to your municipality and city) that need to get on board so you can realize your aspirations and ambitions and/or address identified challenges?*
 - *Guiding question: Think about actors that experience an impact from the identified challenges and about actors that (could) have an impact on the challenges (both positive and negative).*

- EV-INBO and YES (specifically responsible for the CELAC workshops) are available for additional guidance and support before, during and after the workshops, and for guidance for follow-up iterations.

2.1.1 Two-tiered approach

The 'two-tiered approach' can be applied to reduce workload within a tight timeframe. This can be applied when e.g. it is not possible to complete the stakeholder list within one meeting and a second meeting is needed, or when the first meeting is running out of time, to propose to fill in certain elements in a second meeting.

- In the first tier (meeting), participants can agree which challenges are handled first (as they have a higher relevance/importance) and identify stakeholders to those challenges. In the first tier the full ranking of categories is applied.
- In the second tier (meeting), stakeholders to the remaining challenges will be identified. The scoring of categories will be limited to 'benefit of engagement of the stakeholder' (only the qualitative answer). This will still provide some information/motivation to why it is important the stakeholder should be included and possibly invited to the CNA kick-off meeting (see figure 5 in Annex 3 as an example). The remaining categories can be filled in after the first local CNA meeting when updating/revisiting the stakeholder list.

Due to the tight time schedule of the first iteration some cities applied the two-tiered approach to not overburden the participants.

2.2 Workshop: Who are the stakeholders and why?

The knowledge brokers are responsible for organizing workshops with the participants. If data is collected from just one participant, these steps can also be done in the form of an interview.

During the workshop, the first step is to complete the preliminary list of stakeholders (section 2.2.1). In a second step, the participants jointly score these stakeholders based on predefined categories: interest, impact and benefits of engagement (section 2.2.2). The workshop concludes with a final check of the scoring and a discussion on potential conflicts and barriers as well as the next steps to be taken (section 2.2.3). Annex 1 provides a script for the workshop, including practical guidelines for each step in the workshop.

2.2.1 Develop a list of all potentially relevant stakeholders

As a first step, the participants identify all possible stakeholders who can influence or are influenced by the city challenges. The pre-workshop preparation by the participants is used as a starting point. Each participant shortly presents their preliminary list of stakeholders, which is added to the Google sheet.

To further complete the stakeholder list, the questions and stakeholder categories in annex 2 are used to identify overlooked stakeholders.

The identification of stakeholders can be done per city challenge to conduct it in an orderly manner.

At this stage, it is important to ensure that no stakeholder is forgotten in relation to the city challenges. **Civil society** is an important sector to consider if the community or users have a direct interest in the

challenges or restoration activities. It is also important to consider the potential stakeholders in different **geographic or administrative areas** within one organization. Del. 1.6 (Inclusive participatory process for urban ecosystem restoration) provides further recommendations on including underrepresented groups within INTERLACE. When trying to identify these groups, the social challenges this process may represent (discrimination, perception of nature, existing inequalities, potential power relationships between participants, etc.) should be recognized by the knowledge broker and noted in case there is a suspicion that it may result into blind spots in the database. In follow-up iterations, participants should be sought that can fill in these blind spots.

2.2.2 Score all potentially relevant stakeholders using predefined categories

When a list of stakeholders is created, each stakeholder is scored in the following predefined categories: interest, impact by and benefit of engagement.

Note: this can be scored as a general interest in, impact by and benefits of engagement *for the project and restoration activities* (see figure 3 in Annex 3 as example), or this can be scored as interest in, impact by or benefits of engagement *per city challenge* (see figure 4 and 5 in Annex 3 as examples). The latter allows for more detailed motivation for the stakeholder selection for INTERLACE activities, but requires a bigger time investment by the participants to discuss and score.

During the workshop, the facilitator asks the following questions for each identified stakeholder. Each question is first answered in a qualitative way, before assigning a score.

- What interest does the stakeholder have in the city challenge(s)?
 - A qualitative answer motivating the interest of the stakeholder;
 - Score from 0 to 5: no interest, very low, low, medium, high, very high interest.
- What impact does the city challenge(s) have on the stakeholder?
 - A qualitative answer motivating the impact a stakeholder might experience;
 - Score from 0 to 5: no impact, very low, low, medium, high, very high impact.
- How beneficial would engagement of the stakeholder be to the CNA and other local INTERLACE activities?
 - A qualitative answer on what knowledge, expertise or resource the stakeholder could bring to the process
 - Score from 0 to 5: no benefit, very low, low, medium, high, very high benefit.

Participants discuss the qualitative answer and score for each stakeholder and come to a conclusion (rather an accommodation - they can live with the conclusion - than a consensus where everyone agrees). The knowledge brokers who know the city challenges, context and possible stakeholders may give their input during this process. Both the motivation and the score are captured in the Google sheet.

2.2.3 Final check and discussion

A final check is done by discussing the completed stakeholder list. The participants of the workshop discuss whether the scoring makes sense when looking over the whole list as well as the scores in

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relation to each other, especially in the case of very low or very high scores. E.g. by reviewing the stakeholders who scored “very high interest”; does this score still hold up when comparing these stakeholders with each other or should some nuances be made?

Finally, the workshop is concluded with three discussion points:

- Are there any **conflicts**, or potential of conflicts, amongst the stakeholders or between the stakeholders and the city challenge(s) (e.g. conflicting interests, motives, views)?
- Are there any **barriers** to participation and/or engagement (e.g. ability and interest to participate or technical, physical, linguistic, geographical, political, lack of time, information access, knowledge barriers)?
- Are **next steps** necessary to undertake (by the knowledge broker or participants) to complete the stakeholder database?

If the first two questions reveal specific information related to a stakeholder about conflicts or barriers, this should be added in the Google Sheet. More general barriers or (potential) conflicts, or concerns should be noted down separately and shared with the EV-INBO team. The EV-INBO team uses this input for the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (Del. 1.5).

The third question is meant to make arrangements for follow-up steps. E.g. an extra meeting is necessary with the participants to complete the exercise, or based on the discussions some blind spots in the stakeholder list have been discovered and new participants need to be identified to get additional information. A snowball approach can be applied to identify new participants who might be able to share new insights (see section 2.4). New insights and information can be added to the stakeholder database during following iterations as it is a living database.

In every case, arrangements need to be made to collect contact information of the stakeholders. This is done after the workshop (see section 2.3.1)

2.3 Post-workshop: Assemble and analyse the data

The data has been collected but still needs to be completed with contact information (section 2.3.1) in which data protection concerns should be considered (section 2.3.2). Furthermore, the information needs to be transferred to the INTERLACE logbook which is where the living database is stored (section 2.3.3). Finally, the stakeholders can be categorized based on the scoring. The categorization motivates the selection of stakeholders for local INTERLACE activities (section 2.3.4).

2.3.1 Collect contact information

After the workshop, the knowledge broker will share the completed Google sheet and ask the participants to complete the column with the **contact information** of the stakeholders they know. Missing contact information of stakeholders should be added by the knowledge brokers. This can be done by an internet search or by asking people who might have this information (while also explaining the purpose of collecting this information).

2.3.2. Data protection stakeholder database

As contact information is gathered and stored, it is important to follow the GDPR regarding data

protection:

- If the contact information of the stakeholder is publicly available, the data can be stored in the stakeholder database. Most institutional e-mail addresses fall under this.
- When the stakeholder joins a local CNA, they have to sign the information and consent form, which allows the project to collect and process the data. The consent form also provides the option for the stakeholder to remove his contact information from the database.
- In case the contact information of the stakeholder is not publicly available, this information cannot be stored in the database. First, permission must be granted through the information and consent form, even if the stakeholder did not join a local CNA yet.

A column is added next to the contact information in the stakeholder database with the question: “Personal data publicly available or consent form signed?”. The option ‘yes’ should be selected if this is indeed the case. If the option ‘no’ is selected, then the cell with the contact information should be empty.

2.3.3 Assembling the information into the stakeholder database

Each city has their own sheet in the INTERLACE logbook, in which basic information can be found, such as the contact information of city representatives and knowledge brokers, the city challenges, the organized events, etc. The stakeholder database is also part of the logbook. After all the data (including contact information) has been collected in the Google sheet of the workshop, the data can be copied into the INTERLACE logbook, maintaining the same structure. Annex 3 presents some images of the current stakeholder databases in the INTERLACE logbook which can be used as examples for following iterations.

2.3.4 Categorizing the stakeholder database for stakeholder selection

To motivate the selection of stakeholders for upcoming local INTERLACE activities, the identified stakeholders can be categorized according to their interest, impact and benefits of engagement. The categorization is especially relevant when many stakeholders have been identified but the events have only limited space. This categorization is more detailed when the stakeholders have been scored per city challenge. When an event is organized around one or a few specific challenges, the stakeholders related to these challenges are more easily identified.

Figure 2 shows the results of such a categorization exercise for the city of Granollers. In Granollers, stakeholders were categorized per city challenge. The figure presents the categorization for the city challenge ‘water management (reuse and drought)’. The stakeholders are mapped out on two axis according to the scores they received, namely interest (x-axis) and impact (y-axis). Also the score on benefit of engagement is included by presenting that score next to the name of the stakeholder. The shades of green, yellow and red indicate the relevance of inviting the stakeholder to a local INTERLACE event that discusses one specific challenge, from very relevant to not relevant.

In the example of Granollers, dark green indicates that the stakeholder scored high to very high on all categories (interest, impact and benefit for engagement) and are the most important stakeholders to include in relation to that specific city challenge. Lighter shades of green indicate that the stakeholder

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No interest - High to very high impact			Very low to low interest - High to very high impact			Medium interest - High to very high impact			High to very high interest - High to very high impact		
ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement
			6		4	9		3	10		3
			8		2	13		4	17		5
			15		1	71		4	20		5
									21		5
									22		4
									23		4
									38		5
									60		4
									74		3
No interest - Medium impact			Very low to low interest - Medium impact			Medium interest - Medium impact			High to very high interest - Medium impact		
ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement
						14		3	16		3
									52		4
No interest - Very low to low impact			Very low to low interest - Very low to low impact			Medium interest - Low to very low impact			High to very high interest - Low to very low impact		
ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement	ID	Stakeholder	Benefit of engagement
2		1	1		1	12		4	39		4
25		0	3		1				56		4
26		0	4		4						
27		0	5		2						
28		0	7		2						
29		0	11		0						
30		0	18		2						
31		0	19		2						
32		0	24		2						
33		0									
34		0									
35		0									

Figure 2. Snapshot from the stakeholder categorization of Granollers for the city challenge ‘water management (reuse and drought)’. Stakeholder names have been removed for privacy reasons.

scored high to very high on one or two categories, but scored lower on the other(s). These stakeholders are still important to include. Yellow indicates that these stakeholders have an average combined score, and could still be considered to be invited to local INTERLACE activities regarding that city challenge. Red indicates that the stakeholder scored low to very low on most categories, and therefore do not have to be invited to local INTERLACE activities regarding that specific city challenge.

Based on the stakeholder categorization and in dialogue with T2.2 (task responsible for the local CNA), the CFP can select and invite stakeholders for the local CNA and other local INTERLACE activities. Each CNA will have its own focus and topics to be discussed, and stakeholders can be invited in function of the agenda of a particular meeting. For each CNA, it is important to select a balanced group of stakeholders in terms of knowledge, expertise and viewpoints (impacts and interests), including underrepresented groups such as women, people with a low income, migrants, youth, etc. Del. 1.6 provides further recommendations about including such groups within INTERLACE.

2.4 Following iterations of the stakeholder analysis

The identification of stakeholders is a fluid and iterative process, which entails that stakeholders can be added, removed or changed throughout the project as the list of stakeholders is a ‘living database’ that continuously changes over time .

The collection of new data is a fluid and iterative process as well. Data can be updated when new insights appear, e.g. after a local CNA meeting. Missed stakeholders can be identified during a discussion about a local challenge at a local CNA. This can be added immediately to the stakeholder database. However, the same information has to be collected for all identified stakeholders: ask questions (section 2.2.2) to the participant who mentioned these newly identified stakeholders to gain insight on the categories ‘interest’, ‘impact’ and ‘benefits of engagement’.

It is also possible to update the scores of the categories, however this should be properly motivated and reflected in the new scores.

When there are signals (e.g. during the final discussion of the first workshop) that the stakeholder database is incomplete or there are some blind spots (certain stakeholder groups or sectors are missing), then follow-up interviews or workshops are recommended. The steps of section 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3 can be repeated, however the current database can act as a starting point. This avoids repetition and allows the interviews or workshops to focus on unidentified stakeholders or missing scores. Give the participants time to see the stakeholder list before the start of the interview or workshop. This should be a copy of the database where the contact information is left out. It is also not allowed to give external participants access to the INTERLACE logbook.

The stakeholder list can be revisited by CFP members or by new participants, depending on the information needs. To select new participants for a workshop, **snowball sampling** can be applied. It is a method commonly used where initial participants are asked for recommendations for possible new participants based on their network and experience. Snowball sampling methods are heavily influenced by the social networks of the initially contacted people. The city focal points (participants of the first iteration) are a good starting point to identify new participants who can potentially add to the stakeholder list.

A strength of this snowball approach is the integration of the knowledge brokers into 'trust networks'. A limitation can be that certain people who may be important to a city challenge may not be referenced as stakeholder, e.g. because of prejudices that exist within a particular community or group. Snowball sampling thus requires an awareness of its limitations, and can be complemented with other approaches as required for the city challenges.

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Annex 1. Online workshop script

Purpose: Development of an inclusive and relevant stakeholder list with scores on predefined categories: interest in the city challenge(s), impacted by the city challenge(s) and benefit of engagement in the INTERLACE project.

Estimated duration of the workshop: ca. 2 hours

Preparation:

1. Decide (with the CFP) in relation to which city challenge(s) the stakeholders will be identified to. This can be based on an already made prioritization or on missing information from previous workshops.
2. The knowledge brokers send an invitation to the participants and inform them about the purpose and context of the workshop. The participants are asked to prepare the workshop by making an initial list of stakeholders (see section 2.1).
3. An information and consent form should be presented to the participants who are involved for the first time in the INTERLACE project. The consent form should be signed before starting the data collection workshop. The information and consent form can be found on the shared Google drive.
4. Each city received a link to a Google Sheet in which the data of the stakeholder analysis can be collected. If a new empty sheet is needed, please email Michael.leone@inbo.be.
5. One facilitator guides the participants through the exercise; one note-taker completes the Google sheet with the gathered data.
6. EV-INBO for the EU workshops and YES for the CELAC workshops are available for any questions or support during the workshops.

ESTIMATED DURATION	WORKSHOP ELEMENTS
15'	<p>Introduction</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The facilitators introduce the stakeholder analysis (methodology and role in the project) • The participants introduce themselves (when necessary). • The participants receive the possibility to ask questions about the purpose, structure and approach of the stakeholder analysis. • When a two-tiered approach is applied, decide with the participants which city challenges to handle in the first tier, and which city challenges can be handled in the second tier (see section 2.1.1).
10'	<p>Input from pre-workshop tasks</p> <p>The participants present their preliminary stakeholder lists (see section 2.1). These stakeholders are added to the Google Sheet.</p>
30'	<p>Completing the stakeholder list</p> <p>Stakeholders will be added to the preliminary list based on the guiding questions (see annex 2) to ensure a diverse group of stakeholders are identified, including vulnerable groups (see section 2.2.1). It is possible (and preferable!) that interesting discussions arise during the completion of the stakeholder list. This information may be relevant for the following steps of the workshop. However, keep an eye on the time. The note-taker writes the relevant discussion points in a separate document.</p>
45'	<p>Score the stakeholders</p> <p>The participants discuss for each stakeholder consecutively the predefined categories (see section 2.2.2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest; • Impact; • Benefits of engagement. <p>Before giving a score, the participants discuss the motivations (the 'why' or explanation behind the score) by answering the following questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the interest of the stakeholder in the city challenge(s)? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open answer followed by a score from 0 to 5 (no interest to very high interest). • What impact does the city challenge(s) have on the stakeholder? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open answer followed by a score from 0 to 5 (no impact to very high impact). • What benefit will the engagement of the stakeholder have in the project? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Open answer on what expertise, knowledge or resources the stakeholder can bring into the project, followed by a score from 0 to 5 (no benefits to very high benefits of engagement). <p>The participants reach a conclusion over the given scores.</p>

30'	<p>Final check</p> <p>The facilitator discusses the stakeholder list and whether the scoring makes sense when overlooking the whole list and comparing the scores in relation to each other (see section 2.2.3).</p> <p>Afterwards, the following 3 questions are discussed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is there the potential for any conflicts arising amongst stakeholders or between stakeholders and the city challenge(s) (e.g. conflicting interests, motives, views)? 2. Are there any barriers to participation and/or engagement (e.g. ability and interest to participate, barriers such as technical, physical, linguistic, geographical, political, lack of time, information access, knowledge)? - <i>This will be addressed in our 'stakeholder engagement strategy report' in collaboration with Task 2.2.</i> 3. What next steps are necessary to be undertaken by the city focal points to successfully finish the stakeholder analysis?
5'	<p>Wrap up</p> <p>The facilitator wraps up the workshop. The participants are thanked for their collaboration and informed about the next steps of the stakeholder analysis.</p>
After the workshop	<p>Actions</p> <p>Participants are asked to add contact information of stakeholders to which they have access to in the Google sheet (see section 2.3). It is recommended to ask this after the workshop, as some participants might need to search for this information. Knowledge brokers can complete missing contact information by conducting an (online) search.</p> <p>The knowledge brokers process the data collected during the workshop and update the INTERLACE logbook.</p>

Annex 2. Guiding questions for identifying stakeholders

We propose the following guiding questions to ensure all relevant stakeholders are included:

- Who is responsible for making decisions that (might) affect the city challenge(s)?
- Which stakeholders are likely to be affected by the city challenge(s), or by the restoration activities that aim to improve the city challenge(s)?
- Which stakeholders, although not directly affected, may be interested in the city challenge(s), research output or INTERLACE products (project deliverables)?
- Which vulnerable individuals or groups are important to be included?
- Which stakeholders have been involved in similar projects on previous occasions?
- Which stakeholders may be able to provide relevant information, equipment or resources in relation to the city challenge(s), the restoration activities or INTERLACE products (project deliverables)?
- Which stakeholders are likely to have a negative or critical view of the city challenge(s) or restoration activities?
- Which stakeholders are likely to be the most influential towards the city challenge(s) or restoration activities?

Besides the guiding questions, the knowledge broker can also check if all of the following stakeholder groups have been identified (when considered relevant):

- Decision makers
- Policy makers and government institutions
 - National government and entities
 - Regional government and entities
 - Local / municipal authorities and entities
- Experts and advisors
- Scientific community
- Traditional ecological knowledge holders / indigenous knowledge holders (according to context, particularly important for Latin America)
- Education and cultural institutes
- NbS practitioners and Nature-Based Enterprises (NBE's)
- Landowners and land managers

- Private sector
- Finance sector and funders
- NGO's and civil society organizations (including grassroots groups and environmental movements)
- Civil society and community groups
- Children and youth
- Press and media
- Vulnerable individuals and groups/underrepresented groups (e.g. socio-economic status, ethnicity, sex, age, disability):
 - Individuals with a low socio-economic status, living in informal settlements, individuals working in the informal sector (especially if this work is in any way connected to specific urban challenge(s));
 - Ethnic minorities and migrants;
 - Women, with special attention to women with a low SES, single mothers, migrant women or isolated women;
 - Elders, with special attention to socially isolated individuals and elders in retirement homes;
 - Individuals and groups with disabilities;
 - Vulnerable groups due to the Covid-pandemic (e.g. unemployed people, shifts in socio-economic status or unstable economic situations, formerly active stakeholders that no longer have the possibility).

Annex 3. Example images of current stakeholder databases

IDENTIFICACIÓN DE ACTORES - ENVIGADO								
ID	Actor	Categoría	Interés del actor en el reto	Puntuación interés	Impacto del reto en el actor	Puntuación impacto	Beneficio de la participación	¿Por qué (qué conocimientos, experiencia o recursos pueden aportar)?
1		Gobierno local	Mejorar Ordenamiento Ambiental Territorial	5 - Muy alto	Evidencia de la importancia del componente	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Incidencia a largo plazo en la planificación. C
2		Gobierno local	Articulación urbano-rural. Gestión integral	3 - Medio	Gestión ambiental integral. Redes institucion	3 - Medio	3 - Medio	Manejo integral
3		Gobierno local	Identificar prioridades de conectividad (m	5 - Muy alto	Indicadores para tomar decisiones frente a p	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Permisos ambientales, disminución del riesgo
4		Gobierno local		3 - Medio	Inclusión de prioridades ambientales en el d	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Planificación de la red vial y la movilidad sost
5		Gobierno Regional	Mejorar articulación institucional	5 - Muy alto	Modelo lo pueden llevar a otras áreas	4 - Alto	5 - Muy alto	Información ambiental de región (recurso híd
6		Gobierno Regional	Fortalecer áreas protegidas, redes ecológ	4 - Alto	Modelo lo pueden llevar a otras áreas	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Información ambiental urbana, Articulación er
7		Gobierno Regional	Etapas tempranas de la red, pero relevanci	3 - Medio	Acciones ejemplo para diferentes municipios	5 - Muy alto	3 - Medio	Capital técnico del personal vinculado en los
8		Gobierno Regional	Afinidad con el tema, pero la escala de in	3 - Medio	Replicabilidad del modelo y fortalecimiento d	5 - Muy alto	3 - Medio	Conocimiento técnico y acceso a información
9		Gobierno Nacional	Fortalecer el tema de Estructura Ecológic	2 - Bajo	Acciones ejemplo para diferentes municipios	3 - Medio	3 - Medio	Conocimiento técnico y acceso a información
10		Organización de la	Participación frente a decisiones de diseñ	4 - Alto	Información y conocimiento para apropiaciór	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Conocimiento técnico, liderazgo en sistemas
11		Organización de la	Instancia de participación de líderes de d	3 - Medio	Ejemplo de implementación y gestión multia	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Liderazgo y fortalecimiento de redes
12		Organización de la	Participación frente a decisiones de diseñ	4 - Alto	Información y conocimiento para apropiaciór	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Conocimiento técnico, liderazgo en gestión a
13		Organización de la	Instancia de participación de líderes de d	3 - Medio	Ejemplo de implementación y gestión multia	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Liderazgo y fortalecimiento de redes
14		Organización de la	Interés en temas ambientales urbanos a	3 - Medio	Beneficios por presupuestos y proyectos de	3 - Medio	4 - Alto	Socialización, apropiación social
15		Academia	Generar información relevante para mejo	3 - Medio	Oportunidades de implementación en contex	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Participación en diferentes niveles y académi
16		Academia	Generar información relevante para mejo	3 - Medio	Oportunidades de implementación en contex	3 - Medio	4 - Alto	Abundante información sobre Envigado. Con
17		Academia	Generar información relevante para mejo	3 - Medio	Oportunidades de implementación en contex	3 - Medio	3 - Medio	Información ambiental en contextos rurales
18		Academia	Generar información relevante para mejo	3 - Medio	Oportunidades de implementación en contex	3 - Medio	3 - Medio	Información ambiental
19								
20		Organización de la	Interés en temas ambientales urbanos a	3 - Medio	Beneficios por presupuestos y proyectos de	3 - Medio	4 - Alto	Socialización, apropiación social
21		Gobierno local	Procesos educativo y culturales	5 - Muy alto	Avances ambientales en los procesos educa	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Cátedras y experiencias exitosas en temas a
22		Industria local	Proyectos ambientales que surgen desde	3 - Medio	Procesos de articulación con la gestión emp	3 - Medio	4 - Alto	
23								
24		instituciones educa	Proyectos de Educación Ambiental, expe	5 - Muy alto				
25		Gobierno local	Desarrollo de proyectos ambientales	5 - Muy alto	Implementación de proyectos	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Recursos financieros
26		Gobierno Regional	Desarrollo de proyectos ambientales	5 - Muy alto	Implementación de proyectos	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Recursos financieros, procesos de investigaci
27		Organización de la	interés en temas ambientales	3 - Medio	Beneficios por presupuestos y proyectos de	3 - Medio	4 - Alto	Socialización, apropiación social
28		Organización de la	interés en temas ambientales	3 - Medio	Beneficios por presupuestos y proyectos de	3 - Medio	4 - Alto	Socialización, apropiación social
29		Organización de la	Participación frente a decisiones de diseñ	4 - Alto	Información y conocimiento para apropiaciór	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Conocimiento técnico, liderazgo en gestión a
30		Organización de la	Participación frente a decisiones de diseñ	4 - Alto	Información y conocimiento para apropiaciór	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Conocimiento técnico, liderazgo en gestión a
31		Organización de la	Participación frente a decisiones de diseñ	4 - Alto	Información y conocimiento para apropiaciór	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Conocimiento técnico, liderazgo en gestión a
32		Gobierno local	Desarrollo de infraestructura y equipamier	5 - Muy alto	Evidencia de la importancia del componente	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Desarrollo de modelos basados en construc
33		Gobierno local	Participación para los procesos que se d	3 - Medio	Beneficios para la seguridad ciudadana	3 - Medio	3 - Medio	Apoyo policivo
34		Academia	Procesos educativo y culturales	5 - Muy alto	Avances ambientales en los procesos educa	5 - Muy alto	5 - Muy alto	Cátedras y experiencias exitosas en temas a
35		Cultural	Procesos culturales con enfoque ambient	4 - Alto	Avances ambientales en los procesos cultur	4 - Alto	4 - Alto	Proyectos y eventos culturales ambientales

Figure 3. Part of the stakeholder database of Envigado. This example shows that Envigado scored the stakeholders when considering the plans for the interlace project and restoration activities in general. Stakeholder names have been removed for privacy reasons.

STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION			Challenge: Brownfield restoration (heat stress and heat island effect / biodiversity / green space management)							Challenge: Reconnection to the biosphere / Environmental education and awarness (social equi						
ID	Stakeholder	Category	Explanation interest	Score Interest	Explanation impact	Score impact	Why (what knowledge, expertise or resources can they bring)?	Benefit of engagement	Conflict with other stakeholders?	Barriers to participation?	Explanation interest	Score Interest	Explanation impact	Score impact	Why (what knowledge, expertise or resources can they bring)?	Benefit of engagement
1		Government	INTERLACE team leader	5 - Very high	brownfield restoration burden	5 - Very high	Relevant knowledge, contact	5 - very high	with other offices in the		education can	cc 5 - Very high	when citizens are	4 - high	better support of	5 - Very high
2		Government	responsible for SDG implementation	4 - High	practical impact low	2 - Low	contact to stakeholders	4 - High	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	education can	cc 5 - very high	when citizens are	4 - High	better support of	5 - Very high
3		Government	INTERLACE co-team leader	5 - Very high	restoration is part of city goals	5 - very high	Relevant knowledge, contact	5 - Very high	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	education can	cc 5 - Very high	when citizens are	4 - High	better support of	5 - Very high
4		Government	more interested in events	2 - Low	action is not happening on the	1 - Very low	knowledge transfer on plan	3 - Medium	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	education can	cc 4 - High	when citizens are	4 - High	better support of	5 - Very high
5		Government	more interested in events	2 - Low	action is not happening on the	1 - Very low	knowledge transfer on plan	3 - Medium	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	education can	cc 4 - High	when citizens are	4 - High	better support of	5 - Very high
6		Government	creation of new resilient green	5 - Very high	brownfield restoration burden	5 - Very high	Relevant knowledge, contact	5 - Very high	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	education can	cc 5 - Very high	when citizens are	5 - Very high	better support of	5 - Very high
7																
8		Government	increased infiltration area low	3 - Medium	reduced usage of the sewage	3 - Medium	knowledge about possible	2 - Low	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	better education	2 - Low	reduce amount	2 - Low	knowledge about	2 - Low
9		Government	not their field of work	1 - Very low	not their field of work	1 - Very low	contact to other cities	3 - Medium	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	education can	cc 4 - High	when citizens are	2 - Low	better support of	3 - Medium
10		Government	social office	1 - Very low	more interested in social/education	1 - Very low	not their field of work	2 - Low	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	offering education	3 - Medium	no direct impact	2 - Low	mind openness of	3 - Medium
11		Government	youth office	1 - Very low	more interested in social/education	1 - Very low	not their field of work	2 - Low	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	offering education	4 - High	no direct impact	2 - Low	mind openness of	3 - Medium
12		Government	upgrade livability of the city	4 - High	impact depending on actual	3 - Medium	benefit: contact to business	4 - High	with other offices in the	lack of personnel resources	education can	cc 2 - Low	no direct impact	1 - Very low	not the field of work	2 - Low
13		District manager	Bring economic interest to the	5 - Very high	impact depending on actual	5 - Very high	benefit: contact to business	5 - Very high	see citizen platform		education can	cc 3 - Medium	when citizens are	3 - Medium	district managers	2 - Low
14		District Manager														
15		District manager	Bring economic interest to the	5 - Very high	impact depending on actual	5 - Very high	benefit: contact to business	5 - Very high	see citizen platform		education can	cc 3 - Medium	when citizens are	3 - Medium	district managers	2 - Low
16		District manager	Bring economic interest to the	5 - Very high	impact depending on actual	5 - Very high	benefit: contact to business	5 - Very high	see citizen platform		education can	cc 3 - Medium	when citizens are	3 - Medium	district managers	2 - Low
17		District manager	Bring economic interest to the	5 - Very high	impact depending on actual	5 - Very high	benefit: contact to business	5 - Very high	see citizen platform		education can	cc 3 - Medium	when citizens are	3 - Medium	district managers	2 - Low
18		District manager														
19		NGO	environmental NGO	4 - High	NBS in their portfolio	4 - High	knowledge transfer, contact	4 - High	in conflict with other	lack of personnel and	environmental	er 4 - High	increase environ	4 - High	network, education	4 - High
20		NGO/political party	environmental NGO						in conflict with other	lack of personnel and	environmental	er	increase environ		network, education	
21		NGO	environmental NGO	2 - Low	located outside of Chemnitz	1 - Very low	knowledge transfer, contact	1 - Very low	in conflict with other	lack of personnel and	environmental	er 4 - High	increase environ	4 - High	network, education	4 - High
22		NGO														
23		NGO	environmental NGO	4 - High	NBS in their portfolio	4 - High	knowledge transfer, contact	4 - High	in conflict with other	lack of personnel and	environmental	er 4 - High	increase environ	4 - High	network, education	4 - High
24		NGO	environmental NGO	3 - Medium	active at meta level; NBS in the	3 - Medium	knowledge transfer, contact	3 - Medium	in conflict with other	lack of personnel and	environmental	er 4 - High	increase environ	4 - High	network, education	4 - High
25		NGO	social NGO	3 - Medium	NBS only very small part of the	2 - Low	knowledge transfer, contact	3 - Medium	in conflict with other	lack of personnel and	environmental/sc	3 - Medium	increase environ	3 - Medium	network, education	4 - High
26		NGO	environmental NGO	4 - High	active at meta level, more focus	2 - Low	knowledge transfer, contact	3 - Medium	in conflict with other	lack of personnel and	environmental	er 4 - High	increase environ	4 - High	network, education	4 - High
27		NGO	environmental NGO	4 - High	NBS only very small part of the	2 - Low	knowledge transfer, contact	4 - High	in conflict with other	lack of personnel and	environmental	er 4 - High	increase environ	4 - High	network, education	5 - Very high

Figure 4. Part of the stakeholder database of Chemnitz. This example shows that Chemnitz scored the stakeholders per city challenge. Each city challenge has a different colour. Stakeholder names have been removed for privacy reasons.

Living stakeholder database: methodology

STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION				Water management (reuse and drought)					Reconnecting people with nature/environmental					Ecological connectivity and naturaliz					Flood risk: pluvial and		Enhance sustainable agriculture and								
ID	Stakeholder	Category	(Potential) conflicts	Barriers	Contact information	Explanation interest	Score Interest	Explanation impact	Score impact	Benefit of engagement	ources can they bring?/	Explanation interest	Score Interest	Explanation impact	Score impact	Benefit of engagement	ources can they bring?/	Explanation interest	Score Interest	Explanation impact	Score impact	Benefit of engagement	ources can they bring?/	Benefit of engagement	ources can they bring?/	Benefit of engagement	ources can they bring?/		
1					Lack of Gemm	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo		3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	
2					Lack of Gemm	0 - No inte	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo		3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	
3					private Gemm	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo		3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	
4		municipality neighbour			Workin M. Mer	2 - Low	1 - Very lo	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	similar	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High
5		municipality neighbour			Workin José V	2 - Low	1 - Very lo	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low		4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	
6		municipality neighbour			Workin Ventur	1 - Very lo	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	but the	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	
7		municipality neighbour			Workin Margal	actions 2 - Low	1 - Very lo	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low		3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	
8		company	potenti			1 - Very lo	4 - High	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	lack of	2 - Low	4 - High	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	
9		public administration			mcana	3 - Mediur	4 - High	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	functio	2 - Low	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	
10		water management company	potenti		network	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	excess	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	
11		electric company	potenti			1 - Very lo	2 - Low	0 - No ber	0 - No ber	0 - No ber		2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	
12		social entity			They te	3 - Mediur	2 - Low	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	active	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	
13		social entity			info@c	3 - Mediur	5 - Very hi	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	active	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	
14		social entity - generate debate			There	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur		4 - High	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	
15					Genera	1 - Very lo	4 - High	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo	1 - Very lo		3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	
16		consumer association - enviro			lamaqr	4 - High	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	3 - Mediur	consur	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	
17		public administration			lack of Manel	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi		5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	
18		environmental entity			ask Ma	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low		5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	
19		public administration			lack of rebollo	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low	2 - Low		5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	
20		public agency			They a Eve G	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi	5 - Very hi		4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	4 - High	
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Figure 5. Part of the stakeholder database of Granollers. This example shows that Granollers scored the stakeholders per city challenge. Each city challenge has a different colour. They applied a two-tiered approach for the first iteration. Two city challenges (which had a lower prioritization compared to the first three) were only scored on benefits of engagement. As it is a living database, the remaining scores can be completed in a following iteration. Stakeholder names have been removed for privacy reasons.

INTERLACE is a four year project that will empower and equip European and Latin American cities to restore urban ecosystems, resulting in more liveable, resilient and inclusive cities that benefit people and nature.

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Project Partners

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